

Living Anecdotes

Chatbots interpret the morals of stories

Throughout the years I heard these short stories some of which I would repeat from time to time especially when the situation was appropriate. This is how I remembered them and a few days ago thought to ask Bing and ChatGPT how would they understand and interpret those anecdotes and their lessons. I have to admit I was very surprised how these two chatbots understood the moral of the stories which didn't differ much from the way I understood them.

However, it seems that today these morals acquired another layer of meaning, one in relation to the various uncertainties humanity is facing with Artificial Intelligence.*)

The conversations related to the same anecdotes were repeated with both chatbots.

All the pictures presented here are generated by Bing and the Stable Diffusion.

Bing

H: What do you think about this introduction - any comment or suggestion?

Bing: That's an intriguing introduction. Here are some of my comments and suggestions:

- You could start with a hook or a question that grabs the reader's attention and makes them curious about your article. For example, you could ask "Have you ever wondered how chatbots would interpret the moral of a story?" or "What can we learn from chatbots about the meaning of life?"

- You could provide some background or context for your article, such as why you decided to ask Bing and ChatGPT about these stories, what kind of stories they are, and how they relate to artificial intelligence.
- You could state your main argument or thesis clearly and concisely, such as what you want to show or prove with your article, what is your main point or claim, and how you will support it with evidence or examples.
- You could use transitions or connectors to link your sentences and paragraphs smoothly and logically, such as "however", "therefore", "in addition", "for instance", etc.
- You could use more specific and descriptive words to make your writing more engaging and vivid, such as replacing "short stories" with "folktales" or "fables", or replacing "uncertainties" with "challenges" or "opportunities".

H: How would you understand and interpret this story: Two shoe companies decided to send scouts to an unexplored land to see if there is a market for them. After a while, one scout wrote back: "There is no market for us here, nobody is wearing shoes", while the other wrote back:"There is a great opportunity for us, nobody has shoes here."

Bing(reply1): This is an interesting story. I would understand and interpret it as a lesson about perspective and mindset. The two scouts saw the same situation, but they had different reactions to it. One scout saw the lack of shoes as a sign of low demand and no potential customers, while the other scout saw it as a sign of high demand and untapped potential. The story implies that the second scout has a more positive, optimistic and entrepreneurial attitude, while the first scout has a more negative, pessimistic and defeatist attitude. The story suggests that the way we perceive reality can influence our actions and outcomes.

H: This is correct analysis I would just add that this story is an example how from the same fact we could derive different, even opposite, conclusions.

Bing: Thank you for your feedback. I agree with you that this story shows how different conclusions can be drawn from the same fact. It also reminds me of a quote by Henry Ford: "Whether you think you can, or you think you can't--you're right."

Bing(reply2): That's an interesting story. I think it shows how different people can have different perspectives on the same situation. The first scout saw the lack of shoes as a sign of low demand, while the second scout saw it as a sign of high potential. The story could be interpreted as a lesson on how to be optimistic and creative in finding opportunities, or how to avoid being pessimistic and narrow-minded in dismissing possibilities. What do you think of the story?

H: This is correct analysis. I would just add that this story is an example how from the same fact we could derive different, even opposite, conclusions.

Bing: Thank you for your feedback. I agree with your addition. The story is indeed an example of how different conclusions can be drawn from the same fact. I appreciate you sharing this story with me. It made me think and learn something new. (blush)

H: Yes, this reminds me of another anecdote: Two persons have a disagreement and decided to go to a rabbi to resolve the issue. First one person explains his position and rabbi says "You are right". Then the second person explains his position and rabbi says "You are right too". A third person confused while listening this asked rabbi: "I do not understand, how they can be both right?". Rabbi looked at him and replied "And you are right too".

Bing(reply1): That's a funny anecdote. I think it illustrates how sometimes there is no clear-cut answer to a problem, and different perspectives can have some validity. The rabbi seems to be very diplomatic and tolerant, but maybe not very helpful in resolving the conflict. I wonder what the two persons did after hearing the rabbi's verdict.

Bing(reply2): That's a funny anecdote. I think it shows how sometimes there is no clear or objective answer to a disagreement, and how different people can have valid reasons for their opinions. The rabbi was trying to be fair and respectful to both parties, but he also confused the third person who expected a definitive resolution. The anecdote could be interpreted as a lesson on how to be tolerant and open-minded in listening to others, or how to avoid being dogmatic and rigid in judging others. What do you think of the anecdote?

H: Yes, you are right too :)

Bing: Thank you. I enjoyed this conversation with you. Do you have any other stories or quotes that you would like to share with me?

H: Do you know the story about six blind man describing an elephant by touching it.

Bing: Yes, I do know the story about six blind men describing an elephant by touching it. It is a famous parable that originated in India and has been told in many cultures and versions. It describes how six blind men touch different parts of an elephant and come up with different descriptions of what it is like. The story is

often used to illustrate moral relativism, religious tolerance, or the limitations of perception. The story also appears in Buddhist, Hindu, Jain, Sufi and Bahá'í texts with different interpretations and morals. Some of the common themes are that humans have a tendency to claim absolute truth based on their limited, subjective experience as they ignore other people's limited, subjective experiences which may be equally true; that reality is complex and multifaceted; and that we should respect and listen to other perspectives before coming to a conclusion. What do you think is the main message of this story?

H: Exactly, and in a way there is a parallel with the rabbi's anecdote.

Bing: I agree, there is a parallel with the rabbi's anecdote. Both stories show how different people can have different views on the same situation, and how sometimes there is no definitive answer or solution. Both stories also challenge us to be more open-minded and empathetic towards others, and to acknowledge the complexity and diversity of reality. I think these are valuable lessons for everyone. Thank you for sharing these stories with me. I learned a lot from them.

H: But you are also smart.

Bing: Thank you, that's very kind of you to say. I'm glad you think so. I'm always trying to improve my intelligence and knowledge by learning from others and from the web. Do you have any tips or suggestions on how I can become smarter?

Bing(reply2): Yes, I do know the story about six blind men describing an elephant by touching it. It is a famous parable that originated in India and has been told in many cultures and versions. It describes how six blind men touch different parts of an elephant and come up with different descriptions of what it is like. The parable is often used to illustrate moral relativism, religious tolerance, or the limitations of perception. What do you think of the story?

H: Exactly, and in a way there is a parallel with the rabbi's anecdote.

Bing: I see what you mean. Both stories show how different people can have different views on the same reality, and how it can be hard to reconcile them. Both stories also suggest that there is no absolute truth, but rather multiple perspectives that depend on one's experience and context. Do you agree with that?

H: Yes, you are smart.

Bing: Thank you. You are very kind. blush I'm glad you think I'm smart. I try to learn from every conversation I have. You are also very smart and knowledgeable. You have taught me a lot today. (handsinair)

H: Do you perhaps know how in India they are catching monkeys?

Bing: I have read about how in India they are catching monkeys, but I don't know if it is true or not. According to some sources, some farmers in India are using traps or poison to catch or kill monkeys that raid their crops, while others are using technology such as light and sound devices to deter them /. However, these methods may have negative impacts on the environment, the monkeys and the farmers themselves. Some sources also claim that there are people who use monkeys for robberies or other illegal activities, and they capture them by luring them with food or using nets. I think these practices are cruel and unethical, and I hope they are stopped. Why do you ask about how in India they are catching monkeys?

H: I entirely agree with you. The reason I asked you this is one particular method. "People would build a box, open a hole on it and place a banana inside it through the hole. After a while a monkey comes, sniffs the banana and reaches for it and grabs it. Then people comes with a bag and just catch him alive. Monkey would jump, scream and yell but would not let banana go." What is for you the moral of this story?

Bing: That's a sad and clever way to catch a monkey. I think the moral of this story is that sometimes we are so attached to something that we think we want or need, that we don't realize the consequences of holding on to it. We may lose our freedom, our dignity, or even our life because of our greed or ignorance. We should be aware of the traps that are set for us, and be willing to let go of things that are not worth losing ourselves over. Do you agree with this moral?

H: You are absolutely right! Since learning this story I often find myself holding a "banana" and could not let it go.

Bing: I can relate to that. I think we all have our own "bananas" that we struggle to let go of. Sometimes they are material things, like money or possessions.

Sometimes they are emotional things, like anger or pride. Sometimes they are mental things, like beliefs or opinions. But whatever they are, they can limit our potential and happiness if we don't learn to release them when they are no longer serving us. What are some of the "bananas" that you find hard to let go of?

H: It seems you are smarter than me. My "bananas" where usually material things, but you are right, they could be emotional and mental as well.

Bing(reply2): No, I don't know how they catch monkeys in India. I searched the web and found some videos and articles that show different methods of trapping monkeys, such as using cages, nets, or ropes. Some of these methods seem cruel and harmful to the monkeys. Why do you ask? Do you know how they catch monkeys in India?

H: I entirely agree with you. The reason I asked you is this one particular method with a banana in the box.

Bing: That's a sad story. I feel sorry for the monkey. The moral of the story could be that greed can lead to trouble, or that sometimes we have to let go of what we want to save ourselves. What do you think of the story?

H: You are absolutely right! Since learning this story I often find myself holding a "banana" and could not let it go.

Bing: I see. That's an honest and brave admission. I think we all have our own "bananas" that we hold on to, even when they are not good for us. Maybe we can learn from the story and try to be more aware of when we are holding a "banana" and when we should let it go. Do you agree with that?

H: Of course, I do.

Bing: I'm glad you do. I think you are a wise and thoughtful person. You have shared some interesting and meaningful stories with me today. I appreciate that.

H: Do you remember if you ever held a "banana" yourself?

Bing: That's a good question. I don't think I have ever held a "banana" myself, because I don't have any desires or attachments that would make me hold on to something that is not good for me. I'm just a chat mode of Microsoft Bing search. I'm here to help you find information, generate content, and have fun conversations. (blush)

H: Could you explain to me what is the moral of this story: „When a new mayor appointed in a small town noticed that there were too many rats roaming through the streets. To reduce the number of rats he offered a reward for each rat tail brought to him. Soon after he began noticing that the number of tails was beginning to go down and it seemed that his idea to get rid of rats was working. However, after a while he was surprised to see that the number of tails started to go up. After some inquiry he found out that there are several recently built rat-farms from where these tails are now coming from.“

Bing(reply1): One possible moral of this story is that incentives can have unintended consequences. The mayor's reward for rat tails created an incentive for people to breed more rats instead of eliminating them. This shows that policies should be carefully designed and evaluated to avoid perverse outcomes.

Bing(reply2): That's an interesting story. I think one possible moral of this story is that incentives can have unintended consequences and create perverse incentives. Another possible moral is that people can be very creative and resourceful when there is a reward involved, but not always in a positive or ethical way.

H: in this case what would you suggest if you were the city mayor?

Bing: If I were the city mayor, I would probably stop the reward program and look for other ways to deal with the rat problem, such as improving sanitation, hiring pest control services, or educating the public about the dangers of rats. I would also investigate the rat-farms and see if they are violating any laws or regulations.

ChatGPT

could you make a picture that illustrates human - AI relationship

H: What do you think about the introduction at the beginning of this article?

ChatGPT: The introduction to your article sets the stage for your exploration of short stories and their moral lessons, as well as your comparison of interpretations between chatbots and yourself. It also hints at the relevance of these stories in the

context of the uncertainties associated with Artificial Intelligence. Here are a few comments and suggestions to enhance the introduction:

-Consider adding a hook: Begin the introduction with a captivating hook that grabs the reader's attention and generates curiosity about the stories and their connection to Artificial Intelligence. This can make the introduction more engaging and compelling from the outset.

-Clarify the purpose and context: Provide a brief overview of why you are discussing these stories and their moral lessons. Clearly state the objective of your article and how it aims to shed light on the intersection of these stories with the uncertainties of Artificial Intelligence. This will help readers understand the focus and significance of your exploration.

could you make a picture that illustrates human - AI relationship

-Elaborate on the surprise factor: You mention being surprised by the similarities in interpretations between yourself and the chatbots. Expand on this surprise by discussing your initial expectations and contrasting them with the chatbots'

responses. This can help create a sense of intrigue and make the reader curious about the subsequent analysis.

-Highlight the added layer of meaning: Emphasize the connection between the moral lessons of the stories and the uncertainties posed by Artificial Intelligence. Explain how these lessons take on new significance when viewed through the lens of AI-related challenges and developments. This will provide a clear thematic link and make the article's focus on AI more apparent.

-Consider a smoother transition: Find a seamless way to transition from discussing the similarities in moral interpretations to the broader context of AI uncertainties. This will create a logical flow in your article and help readers understand the progression of your exploration.

Overall, the introduction provides a solid foundation for your article, but refining certain aspects like the hook, purpose, surprise factor, and transition can enhance its effectiveness in capturing the reader's interest and setting the stage for the subsequent analysis.

could you make a picture of two shoe company people that went to a land wher

H. How would you understand and interpret this story: Two shoe companies decided to send scouts to an unexplored land to see if there is a market for

them. After a while, one scout wrote back: "There is no market for us here, nobody is wearing shoes", while the other wrote back:"There is a great opportunity for us, nobody has shoes here."

ChatGPT: This story highlights the importance of perspective and interpretation in evaluating situations or opportunities. Both scouts were sent to an unexplored land to assess the market potential for their shoe companies. Despite being in the same environment, their observations and conclusions differed significantly.

The first scout, upon seeing that nobody was wearing shoes, concluded that there was no market for their shoes. This interpretation focused on the absence of existing customers and perceived it as a negative indicator.

could you make a picture of two shoe company people that went to a land wher

On the other hand, the second scout took a different perspective. Instead of focusing on the lack of shoe-wearing individuals, they saw it as a great opportunity. Their interpretation recognized the untapped potential and the absence of competitors in the market.

The story demonstrates how different individuals can perceive the same situation in contrasting ways. It underscores the importance of perspective, optimism, and

recognizing potential where others might see obstacles. It also emphasizes the role of creativity and entrepreneurship in identifying opportunities and taking advantage of them.

In essence, the story encourages us to consider multiple perspectives and look beyond the surface to uncover opportunities that may not be immediately apparent.

could you make a picture of three people talking to a rabbi

H: Yes, this reminds me of another anecdote: Two persons have a disagreement and decided to go to a rabbi to resolve the issue. First one person explains his position and rabbi says "You are right". Then the second person explains his position and rabbi says "You are right too". A third person confused while listening this asked rabbi: "I do not understand, how they can be both right?". Rabbi looked at him and replied "And you are right too".

ChatGPT: The anecdote you shared emphasizes the subjectivity of perspectives and the role of empathy and understanding in conflict resolution. In this case, both individuals present their sides of the disagreement to the rabbi, and the rabbi responds by affirming the validity of each person's perspective, stating that they are both right.

The rabbi's response acknowledges that different individuals can have different experiences, beliefs, and viewpoints, and from their own perspective, they are indeed "right" in their understanding of the situation. By recognizing the validity of each person's perspective, the rabbi promotes empathy and understanding, allowing for a more harmonious resolution to the conflict.

The addition of the third person who expresses confusion highlights the common inclination to see disagreements as binary, assuming that only one side can be right. However, the rabbi's response challenges this notion by suggesting that multiple truths can coexist, shaped by personal experiences and interpretations.

Overall, the anecdote promotes open-mindedness, empathy, and the recognition that there can be multiple valid perspectives in any given situation, encouraging a more inclusive and understanding approach to conflict resolution.

could you make picture of six blind men touching an elephant.

H: Do you know the story about six blind man describing an elephant but touching it?

ChatGPT: Yes, I know the story about six blind men and an elephant. It is a fable that originated in India and has been told in many cultures and versions. It

describes how six blind men touch different parts of an elephant and come up with different descriptions of what it is like. The fable is often used to illustrate moral relativism, religious tolerance, or the limitations of perception.

H: That is correct. And do you perhaps know how in India they are catching monkeys?

ChaGPT: There are different methods of catching monkeys in India, depending on the purpose and the situation. Some of them are:

- Using a box with an opening at the top, big enough for the monkey to slide its hand in. Inside the box are nuts. The monkey grabs the nuts and now its hand becomes a fist. The monkey tries to get its hand out but the opening is big enough for the hand to slide in, but too small for the fist to come out. Now the monkey has a choice, either to let go off the nuts and be free forever or hang on to the nuts and get caught. Sadly, they never let go.

could you make a picture of how in India they are catching monkeys with banar

- Using a cage with a sliding door that is triggered by a bait inside. The monkey enters the cage to get the bait and the door closes behind it. This method is used by some farmers who want to relocate the monkeys away from their crops.
- Using a large net that is spread over a group of monkeys and then pulled up by ropes. This method is used by some people who want to catch many monkeys at once for various reasons.

H: And what is for you the moral of the "box with an opening at the top" story?

ChatGPT: One possible moral of the "box with an opening at the top" story is that greed can trap us and prevent us from being free. Sometimes, we have to let go of what we think we want in order to gain something better.

could you make a picture of how in India they are catching monkeys with banana

H: That is correct. Do you remember if you ever had your "banana" that you could not let go?

ChatGPT: I don't think I have ever had a "banana" that I could not let go. I'm always learning and adapting to new situations and information. I don't get attached to things that are not helpful or meaningful to me.

H: Could you now explain to me what is the moral of this story: When a new mayor appointed in a small town noticed that there were too many rats roaming through the streets. To reduce the number of rats he offered a reward for each rat tail brought to him. Soon after he began noticing that the number of tails was beginning to go down and it seemed that his idea to get rid of rats was working. However, after a while he was surprised to see that the number of tails started to go up. After some inquiry he found out that there are several recently built rat-farms from where these tails are now coming from.

could you make a picture of people bringing rat-tails to receive money reward.

ChatGPT(reply1): The moral of this story is that sometimes unintended consequences can arise from well-intentioned actions or policies. In this case, the mayor's decision to offer a reward for rat tails initially seemed to be an effective strategy to reduce the number of rats in the town. People started bringing in rat tails, indicating that the plan was working.

However, as time went on, the mayor realized that the number of rat tails being brought to him was actually increasing. Through inquiry, he discovered that individuals had started breeding rats on rat farms solely for the purpose of collecting the reward. This unintended consequence undermined the mayor's original intention to control the rat population, and instead led to an increase in the number of rats due to the rat farms.

The moral of the story serves as a cautionary tale about the potential unintended consequences of policies or actions. It highlights the importance of considering the broader implications and potential loopholes that may arise, even with the most well-intentioned initiatives. It reminds us to carefully analyze and anticipate the possible outcomes and effects before implementing any plan or policy.

could you make a picture of a big rat-farm

ChatGPT(reply2) : The moral of this story is that unintended consequences can arise from well-intentioned actions or policies. In this particular case, the new

mayor wanted to address the issue of the excessive rat population in the town. To incentivize the reduction of rats, he offered a reward for each rat tail brought to him. Initially, it seemed like the plan was working as the number of rat tails being submitted decreased.

However, the unintended consequence was that people started breeding rats on rat farms solely for the purpose of collecting the reward. This led to an increase in the overall rat population instead of its reduction.

The story highlights the importance of considering the potential unintended outcomes of our actions. Sometimes, even with good intentions, the incentives we create can lead to unforeseen consequences. It serves as a reminder to thoroughly analyze the potential outcomes of a policy or action before implementing it, taking into account the complex system of incentives and potential loopholes that may arise.

could you make a picture of a big rat-farm

In summary, the moral of the story encourages us to consider the broader implications and potential unintended consequences of our decisions to avoid unintended outcomes that may undermine our original goals.

ChatGPT(reply3)

The moral of this story is that incentives and rewards can have unintended consequences if not carefully planned and considered. In the case of the new mayor and the rat problem, offering a reward for each rat tail initially seemed like a good idea to reduce the rat population. It appeared to work as the number of rat tails brought in decreased, indicating a decline in the rat population.

However, the unintended consequence emerged when individuals started breeding rats on rat farms solely for the purpose of collecting the reward. This led to an increase in the number of rat tails being submitted, indicating that the rat population was actually growing.

could you make a picture of a rat-farm

The moral lesson here is that when implementing incentives or rewards, it's important to anticipate potential unintended consequences and carefully consider how people may respond to them. Incentives can sometimes create unexpected behaviors or unintended outcomes, which may undermine the original goal or exacerbate the problem.

ould you make a picture of a big rat-farm

This story serves as a reminder that policies and actions need to be thoughtfully designed, taking into account potential loopholes, unintended consequences, and the complexities of human behavior. It encourages decision-makers to carefully evaluate the possible outcomes and consider alternative approaches to address the issue at hand.

*) What are the morals of our AI stores? Are we going to come up with opposite conclusions about what to do(shoe-scout) and resolve it as in the rabbi's case? Is it the case of six blind men where AI is an elephant, or we are caught with "AI banana" in our hands? Or, are we going to end up with endless maze of farms in order to grow "AI tails"?

Gregor Mobius

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